

Kinetics of the Formation of Chalkone-Linear Free Energy Relationships

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The kinetics of the base catalysed condensation of benzaldehyde with substituted acetophenones have been studied. The parameters of the Arrhenius equation and transition state theory have been determined. The applicability of the Hammett equation has been discussed. The effective sigma values and the para resonance interaction energy values for various substituents have been determined.

THE carbonyl condensation reactions are of wide utility in synthetic organic chemistry. Welch¹ studied the kinetics of the reaction of formaldehyde and malonic ester in the presence of dilute alkali. Bell² has investigated the kinetics of aldol condensation in basic medium by dilatometric method. Gettler and Hammett³ have thoroughly studied the kinetics and mechanism of the acid and base catalysed aldol condensation of benzaldehyde with methyl ethyl ketone. Ballester and Bertlett⁴ have studied the kinetics of base-catalysed condensation of phenacyl chloride and benzaldehyde in dioxan-water mixtures. Noyce and Pryor⁵ have discussed the kinetics and mechanism of the acid catalysed condensation of benzaldehyde and acetophenone. The kinetics and mechanism of the reaction of butanone with benzaldehyde have been investigated by Stiles and coworkers⁶. Very recently we have reported⁷ the kinetics of the base catalysed condensation of acetophenone with substituted benzaldehydes.

In the present communication, we have studied the kinetics of the reaction of benzaldehyde with substituted acetophenones. A novel feature of $\rho\sigma$ relationship has been discussed.

Experimental

The acetophenones were prepared and purified by our previous method⁸.

The method of rate measurement was similar to our previous work⁷. The rate constants were computed by using a second order rate equation with the help of least square method. The measured rate constants were all accurate to within 2-3% by agreement between duplicate experiments. The activation parameters were calculated by using appropriate equations. The values of E_a and ΔS^\ddagger were computed with an accuracy of ± 0.5 KCal./mole and 0.8 entropy unit respectively.

Effect of substituent:

The reaction has been observed to obey the second order rate law. The rate is first order in acetophenone as well as benzaldehyde.

It is clear from the data in Table 1 that the reaction is enhanced by electron attracting substituents and retarded by electron repelling groups. The observed rate conform to the following order of reactivity

This is further confirmed from the positive ρ -value⁹.

TABLE—1. VALUES OF THE SPECIFIC REACTION RATE, ENERGY AND ENTROPY OF ACTIVATION

[Substrate]=0.025(M), [Base]=0.1 (M)

Substituent	$k_{10} \times 10^4$ (lit mole ⁻¹ Sec ⁻¹)	E (K.Cal/ mole)	log PZ	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (Cal/deg)
H	19.78	9.90	7.65	41.40
p-nitro-	220.70	8.70	7.97	40.30
m-nitro-	201.20	9.00	7.08	39.70
p-bromo-	41.67	8.30	6.94	45.00
p-chloro-	48.33	8.80	7.33	43.20
p-iodo-	38.33	8.00	6.68	46.00
p-methyl-	5.28	9.20	6.68	46.20
p-methoxy-	4.21	10.10	7.46	43.30
m-methyl	10.00	10.60	7.56	42.00
m-chloro-	39.45	9.20	7.82	42.20
m-bromo-	38.95	9.50	7.75	42.80
3, 4-dimethyl-	5.23	11.00	7.98	40.20
3-nitro, 4-methoxy-	56.62	9.20	7.70	41.50
3-nitro, 4-methyl-	66.68	8.30	7.13	44.10
3-nitro, 4-ethoxy-	60.01	9.70	8.04	40.90
3-nitro 4-chloro-	109.40	7.50	6.82	40.50

Energy and Entropy of Activation :

A linear plot between $\log PZ$ vs $1/\sqrt{E}$ indicates that the reaction obeys Fairclough-Hinshelwood relationship¹⁰.

A linear relationship between the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) and enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) has been observed¹¹ and the value of ' β ', the isokinetic temperature was calculated to be 460°K. Thus there is compensation between the two parameters. This type of plot has been criticised by Peterson¹², but the same conclusions can be obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log k_{303}$ vs. $\log k_{313}$ using Exner's method¹³, which also predicts that selectivity decreases as temperature increases¹⁴.

Hammett equation :

A regression line was fitted to the $\log k$ values against σ° data¹⁵ for the meta-substituted compounds. The reaction constant ρ at 40°, the correlation coefficient ' r ' and the intercept with the ordinate were found to be 1.60, 0.95 and 1.29 respectively.

The correlation is significantly improved by using the Yukawa-Tsuno equation¹⁶ as represented below

$$\log k/k_0 = \rho[\sigma + r(\sigma^- - \sigma)]$$

The value of the coefficient r is found from the slope of the plot of $\rho^{-1} \log k/k_0$ vs. $(\sigma^- - \sigma)$ to be 0.32. The plot of $\log k/k_0$ vs. $[\sigma + 0.32(\sigma^- - \sigma)]$ gives $\rho = 1.85$, with correlation coefficient 0.987.

Considering several reaction series and numerous data, it has been suggested by Van Bekkum and co-workers¹⁷ that in those cases where a substituent enters into mesomeric para interaction with the reaction centre, a multiplicity of (exalted) sigma values is observed. This holds for $+M$ as well as $-M$ substituents. But in the absence of mesomeric para-interaction, sigma values are reasonably constant. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) were calculated from the expression

$$\bar{\sigma} = \frac{\log k - \log k_0}{\rho}$$

As the effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) in general are not suitable criteria for judging mesomeric para interactions, free energy difference terms have been calculated for evaluation of mesomeric para interactions¹⁸.

$$\Delta\Delta F_{para} = -2.303 RT\rho(\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0)$$

This expression involves not only the exaltation of sigma but of ρ and T as well. The effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) and the corresponding para resonance energy differences are given in Table 2.

The magnitude of the resonance interaction in the transition state is quite small in comparison with, for example, the solvolysis of α, α -4-methyl benzyl chloride¹⁹, a reaction for which $\Delta\Delta F_{para}$ is -1.17 K.Cal/mole and which presumably involves an incipient carbonium ion. But it must be emphasised

TABLE 2—EFFECTIVE SIGMA VALUES AND PARA RESONANCE INTERACTION ENERGY VALUES

Substituent	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl	<i>p</i> -Br	<i>p</i> -NO ₂
σ	-0.311	-0.3052	+0.33	+0.283	+0.7494
$\bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0$	-0.191	-0.155	+0.06	+0.023	-0.071
$\Delta\Delta F_p$ in K.Cal/mole	-0.4142	-0.3364	-0.1314	-0.05	-0.1631

that the influence of resonance interactions in the transition state is to be judged by the magnitude of such interaction compared with that of the polar contribution to the free energy of activation i.e. by the ratio

$$\Delta\Delta F_p/2.303 RT\sigma_0 = \bar{\sigma} - \sigma_0/\sigma_0$$

It is evident from our result that the effective sigma values ($\bar{\sigma}$) for para-methoxy ($\bar{\sigma} = -0.31$) and para-methyl ($\bar{\sigma} = -0.305$) differ from σ_0 values. The enhanced values indicate important and substantial increase of resonance interaction between the substituent and the reaction centre in the transition state. Our result is in good agreement of the transition state which may be represented as follows

In the transition state the bond between the methylene group and the carbonyl group develops enol double bond character and this double bond gets into direct conjugation with para-methoxy or para-nitro group. Thus increased resonance is possible both in case of para-nitro group and para-methoxy group in the transition state but not in the ketone state where the bond in question can not develop double bond character. This is further confirmed from the negative sign of the para resonance interaction energy values ($\Delta\Delta F_p$ values) both for the nitro and methoxy group.

For the para-chloro and para-bromo groups there is good agreement between $\bar{\sigma}$ and σ_0 values indicating thereby that there appears to be no stabilisation of the transition state through the operation of $+M$ effect²⁰.

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